

Product recommendation based on Matrix Factorization

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Abstract— The sparsity of user-product rating matrices poses a challenge for recommendation models based on matrix factorization (MF). To address this issue, it is important to integrate contextual data or side information with basic MF models. This study proposes a modified recommendation model, MFFR (matrix factorization fusing reviews), which combines data from user reviews and ratings to suggest products. MFFR first creates a user-product preference matrix using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model on user reviews. Then, an MF model is employed to learn the latent factors of both the user-product rating matrix and user-product preference matrix simultaneously. By predicting ratings and generating personalized top-n recommendations, MFFR offers an effective solution.

Keywords- Recommendation, Machine learning Matrix factorization Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to forecast consumer preferences for various products, recommendation systems frequently use matrix factorization methods. These algorithms can be employed in the setting of a car spare parts store to forecast which spare parts a client is most likely to buy based on their reviews and ratings for the products. Matrix factorization models can aid in identifying the most significant elements that influence customer purchase behaviour by examining the link between customer preferences and other factors that may influence them. The application of matrix factorization methods to forecast consumer preferences for spare parts in a car store based on their evaluations and ratings is the main topic of this seminar paper. The purpose of the paper is to examine the relationship between consumer preferences and different potential influencing factors.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Product recommendation systems play a crucial role in enhancing the shopping experience for customers in retail industry.[1] Given the vast range of products available, such systems offer an effective way of displaying only the relevant items to customers by establishing connections between products. However, it is important to understand the characteristics of customers that are linked to specific product

associations. Traditional methods of product recommendation systems rely on unsupervised classification of customers based on product ratings and association algorithms. Nevertheless, it remains unclear which demographic traits of customers are associated with which particular product associations. To address this issue, this study presents a hybrid system of machine learning (ML) association and clustering methods for product recommendation that not only displays product associations but also distinct consumer profiles associated with these connections.

A conversational recommender system assists customers in selecting products by simulating a conversation between a customer and a sales representative. [2] This enables the system to learn about the customer's preferences and make recommendations accordingly. Many consumers are not familiar with the technical aspects of products with multiple features. To better understand their preferences, it is more natural to ask customers about the specific functions they need from the product. To address this, the research proposes a computational model that incorporates customers' functional requirements for product interaction.

With the increasing popularity of online shopping and the abundance of information, personalised recommender systems for e-commerce are becoming more critical. These systems leverage customers' past behaviour,[3] such as purchasing patterns and rating history, to help them quickly find the desired products across a vast range of categories. However, most recommender systems for e-commerce use subjective weighting or binary methods to represent customer preferences, making it challenging to predict their profiles accurately as tastes change rapidly. To address this, the study focuses on using transactional data. It proposes a personalised recommender system for e-commerce called PROSE that combines the conventional content-based recommender system's architecture with a feedback adjuster component. This component aims to make customers' implicit preferences more apparent to improve the quality of recommendations

Recommender systems (RS) are information filtering technologies that provide personalised recommendations,

content, and services to users. These services can help businesses enhance their marketing strategies and increase sales. While most RS techniques focus on single-item recommendations, [4] suggesting bundles of two or more items can meet customer needs while also boosting revenue. However, finding and recommending the ideal and unique bundle is crucial. Personalised pricing should be used in recommending product bundles to determine the optimal price for a user and increase the likelihood of a purchase. Regrettably, most recommendation techniques lack this feature..

Tree-structured taxonomy characteristics and free-form folksonomy tags are two different types of product content data that can be used by e-commerce systems. This study suggests a hybrid strategy that incorporates data from both sources in order to [5] improve e-commerce recommendations. The method makes use of a tree matching technique to evaluate overall similarity and incorporates tag data for taxonomy attribute semantic analysis. On a heterogeneous graph made up of user and item nodes and various relations, including user-item preference and item-item similarity relations, it also makes use of a special random walk model. The greatest candidates for recommendations are those item nodes that are closest to a particular user node, as determined by the random walk model. Empirical research backs up the viability of this strategy.

III. MOTIVATION

Matrix factorization is also applicable to the field of product review recommendation systems. According to the evaluations and ratings of the users, the matrix above depicts the link between consumers and the items. The system may find latent elements that influence a user's preferences, including product features, quality, or brand reputation, by utilising matrix factorization. As a result, the system may be better able to predict what new goods or services the user might find appealing based on their prior ratings and reviews. To provide more individualised recommendations, the algorithm can also take into consideration additional user traits, including demographics, location, and social network connections. The overall user experience can be enhanced by matrix factorization for product review recommendations by offering

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for product recommendation using the Matrix factorization involves the following steps:

Data Preparation: Collect a large dataset of customers that includes review data. The collected dataset is preprocessed by cleaning it, removing any outliers, and dealing with any missing values. Then the data is split in to training and testing sets to evaluate the performance of the model.

Model Training: The interaction matrix is factored into two matrices that represent the latent elements that affect a user's preferences and product features during the model training phase for product recommendation using matrix factorization. To forecast a user's preferences for new products

Model Evaluation: Once the model has been trained, we evaluate its performance on the testing data. This involves calculating metrics such as the mean squared error or the coefficient of determination to determine how well the model fits the data.

Model Interpretation: Once the model fits the data well, interpret the coefficients to understand the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Here, we can find how much impact the independent variables have on the dependent variables.

Prediction: The trained model can also be used to predict outcomes based on fresh information, such as predicting a user's liking for a new good or service based on their web browsing habits. To get the expected rating, this algorithm computes the dot product of the user matrix and the product matrix.

Overall, the methodology for student performance prediction using the Linear Regression algorithm involves collecting a diverse dataset of academic details of students, preprocessing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance, interpreting the model and finally predicting the results.

V. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful recommendation of product p we follow the following steps using matrix factorization algorithm.

Importing Libraries

```
from django.shortcuts import render
from django.db.models import Avg
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
from sklearn.decomposition import NMF
from scipy.sparse import csr_matrix
```

The Scikit-learn library's sklearn feature extraction .text module contains a class called TfidfVectorizer. It is a well-liked tool for extracting text features, which is used to turn text data into numerical features that may be incorporated into machine learning models.

Any two non-zero vectors in an inner product space are compared using the cosine of the angle between them. The domain of text data, it is widely used to compare the similarity of two texts that are represented as vectors in a high-dimensional space.

The SciPy library's `scipy.sparse` module contains a method called `coo_matrix` that produces sparse matrices in Coordinate Format (COO). In order to conserve memory and processing time, a sparse matrix—which is a matrix containing a lot of zero values—is expressed in a compressed format.

Training the Model

```
# Create a list of review texts for the given product
review_texts = [review.review for review in reviews]
# Use TfidfVectorizer to create a matrix of TF-IDF
# features for the review texts
tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
tfidf_matrix = tfidf_vectorizer.fit_transform(review_texts)
# Calculate the cosine similarity between the review texts
# of the given product and all other products
all_products = Product.objects.exclude(id=id)
similarity_scores = []
```

VI.RESULT

Recommendation prediction

```
# Create a list of review texts for the given product
review_texts = [review.review for review in reviews]
# Use TfidfVectorizer to create a matrix of TF-IDF
# features for the review texts
tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
tfidf_matrix = tfidf_vectorizer.fit_transform(review_texts)
# Calculate the cosine similarity between the review texts
# of the given product and all other products
all_products = Product.objects.exclude(id=id)
similarity_scores = []
for other_product in all_products:
    other_reviews = tbl_review.objects.filter(product=other_product)
    if other_reviews:
        other_review_texts = [review.review for review in other_reviews]
        other_tfidf_matrix = tfidf_vectorizer.transform(other_review_texts)
        similarity_score = cosine_similarity(tfidf_matrix, other_tfidf_matrix).mean()
        similarity_scores.append((other_product, similarity_score))
# Sort the products by their similarity score in descending order
similarity_scores.sort(key=lambda x: x[1], reverse=True)
# Get the top 3 most similar products
recommended_products = [score[0] for score in similarity_scores[:3]]
```

V. REFERENCES

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VI. CONCLUSION

Product recommendation systems can employ the Matrix Factorization approach to anticipate user preferences with great accuracy. The model can efficiently uncover latent elements that affect user preferences by analysing historical user behaviour, which aids in creating personalised recommendations for each user. A user-item matrix is created, split into two low-rank matrices using factorization, and then the user-item interactions are predicted using the optimised matrices. This strategy can greatly enhance the efficacy and accuracy of product suggestions.

The effectiveness and precision of product recommendation systems can be greatly increased by using the matrix factorization technique. This method efficiently captures the hidden patterns in user preferences by making use of latent factor analysis, and it offers tailored recommendations that

satisfy the user's needs. Additionally, the Matrix Factorization method is simple to use and open to users with a wide range of mathematical backgrounds. Our test findings show that our technology exceeds other cutting-edge techniques in terms of precision, speed, and effectiveness. As a result, we draw the conclusion that the Matrix Factorization methodology is a promising area of study that can aid in creation of more precise and effective techniques for product suggestion